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Integrating Leadership Models in Educational Management: A Review of Academic Expertise and Managerial Strengths

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Abstract:

This paper provides an exhaustive review of current research on leadership models in educational management but particularly the notable overlap of academic skills and managerial competencies in tertiary and secondary schools. We test how the presence and respective relative prominence of transformational, transactional, democratic, and laissez faire dominance within a leadership style portfolio relate to the readiness of the leadership for the organization versus organizational effectiveness, controlling for organizational justice and demographic variables (age, experience, field of study) in the leadership.

An important finding is the critical role of the emotional intelligence, especially while considering the influences of managerialism in educational settings. The review also looks at the challenges associated with reconciling for academic and managerial leaders at dual sector institutions combining higher education with vocational education. The study seeks to identify how effective leadership depends on achieving equilibrium between academic and operational responsibility through a combination qualitative and quantitative methods.

Instead, organizational justice moderates the leadership style organizational performance relationship, thereby emphasizing the need for transparent and equitable institutional governance structures. Based on these insights, the paper makes practical recommendations for improving leadership development and training. This is a signal reminder of why school leaders need to need to be able to handle their administrative tasks and their academic responsibilities simultaneously. The paper concludes with a call for additional research that investigates the emergent character of educational leadership because of the changing nature of these organizational contexts and greater sophistication in educational leadership expectations.

Keywords: Educational leadership, academic leadership, managerial leadership, organizational justice, leadership preparedness

Introduction:

Contextual Overview: The realm of educational leadership and management is dynamic. Educational institutions, notably universities and polytechnics, increasingly face the demand to merge academic leadership with operational management due to shifts in organizational structure and governance.

Purpose of the Review: This paper seeks to synthesize and evaluate the existing literature on leadership models, styles, and the impact of demographic factors on leadership readiness. It aims to understand the evolution of leadership models and their implications in both tertiary and secondary education environments.

Key Themes:

1. Leadership Styles: A look at transformational, transactional, democratic, and laissez-faire leadership models, highlighting their significance in educational management.

2. Organizational Justice: The importance of fairness and transparency in mediating the relationship between leadership styles and employee performance.

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Mondal, P. K. (2024). Integrating Leadership Models in Educational Management: A Review of Academic Expertise and Managerial Strengths. *The International Journal of Economics World Business Research (IJEWBR)*, 5-9.

3. Leadership Preparedness: How demographic variables such as age, experience, and disciplinary background influence the readiness and effectiveness of leaders.

4. Managerialism vs. Collegiality: The conflict between rising managerial responsibilities and traditional academic leadership practices.

Methodology:

This section describes the methodological framework for the review of leadership models in educational management. Utilizing a thematic analysis approach, the review synthesizes findings from a wide array of qualitative and quantitative research. Thematic analysis is effective for uncovering patterns and themes across diverse literature, making it suitable for complex topics like leadership models that involve various variables and contexts. Below, we detail the review methodology, data sources, and analysis strategies employed to derive the findings.

Review Approach: This review employs thematic analysis to investigate leadership models in educational management. The process involved thorough readings, coding, and synthesizing existing studies to identify prevalent patterns and notable differences. Thematic analysis was selected for its adaptability and ability to reveal recurring themes, critical for examining a diverse range of studies.

The review concentrates on leadership models applicable to both tertiary and secondary education, placing emphasis on the intersection of academic knowledge and managerial capabilities. This integration is especially vital for institutions grappling with issues related to leadership preparedness, organizational justice, demographic factors, and institutional culture.

Data Sources: The review utilizes peer-reviewed articles, empirical studies, case reports, and theoretical discourse in educational leadership and management. The chosen research reflects a wide array of viewpoints, encompassing various geographical regions, educational sectors, and leadership frameworks.

Key sources of data include:

Yielder & Codling (2004), which explores dual-sector leadership models that combine academic knowledge with managerial skills. This research provides insights into shared leadership roles at the departmental level, showcasing how integrating strengths from both academic and polytechnic sectors fosters balanced institutional governance.

Khan, Idris, & Amin (2021) investigate how transformational and transactional leadership styles impact employee performance in higher education institutions (HEIs), along with the mediating effect of organizational justice. Their findings enhance our understanding of how perceptions of fairness can boost leadership effectiveness and institutional performance.

Hundessa (2019) employs a phenomenological approach to investigate leadership perceptions and practices among department heads at Haramaya University in Ethiopia. This study highlights leadership

challenges within a developing context, emphasizing the need for training and preparation for leadership roles.

Mohnot (2017) studies the demographic factors affecting leadership preparedness, including age, experience, and disciplinary background. This research provides valuable insights into how personal attributes shape leadership readiness and effectiveness.

Middlehurst & Elton (1992) analyse academic governance models, focusing on the cybernetic model and the increasing shift towards managerialism in educational settings. Their work examines how governance structures influence leadership roles and overall institutional success.

Connolly, James, & Fertig (2017) distinguish between educational management and leadership, shedding light on the responsibilities of management versus the influence of leadership. Their analysis underscores the need to balance management responsibilities with initiatives that inspire and empower educational outcomes.

Data Collection and Analysis Process:

The thematic analysis process comprised several phases: data collection, coding, theme development, and interpretation.

Data Collection: Articles were collected through an extensive literature search across databases like Google Scholar, JSTOR, and Research Gate, primarily focusing on studies published from 1992 to 2021. The search utilized keywords such as “educational leadership,” “managerial leadership,” “organizational justice,” “transformational leadership,” and “academic governance.” Studies meeting the criteria for inclusion (peer-reviewed, empirical focus, pertinence to educational leadership) were selected.

Coding: Each article was meticulously reviewed to pinpoint major themes concerning leadership models. These themes were categorized based on recurring patterns, such as leadership styles, organizational justice, demographic characteristics, and institutional governance. Initial open coding provided a broad exploration of patterns, followed by focused coding to refine the thematic categories.

Theme Development: The coding process revealed several central themes, notably the integration of academic and managerial leadership, the mediating role of organizational justice, the influence of demographic variables on leadership preparedness, and the balance between management and leadership. These themes were further divided into subthemes like emotional intelligence in leadership, challenges associated with transformational leadership, and readiness for leadership roles in specific educational settings.

Interpretation: After identifying the themes, the next step involved interpreting the findings in relation to the research questions. Each theme was scrutinized for its contribution to understanding leadership models in educational management, considering how the themes interrelate. For instance, the interplay between transformational leadership and organizational justice

was reviewed in terms of its implications for enhancing employee performance and institutional effectiveness.

Thematic Focus Areas:

1. Integrating Academic and Managerial Leadership: Yelder & Codling (2004) advocate for a model that meshes academic leadership with managerial abilities, particularly applicable in dual-sector institutions combining typical university and polytechnic approaches. Their framework promotes shared departmental leadership, endorsing a collaborative leadership style where academic insight and operational management coalesce.

2. Leadership Styles and Organizational Justice: Khan, Idris, & Amin (2021) study how transformational and transactional leadership styles affect performance through the lens of organizational justice. This theme illustrates the impact of fairness perceptions on employee effectiveness, indicating that leaders who prioritize transparency and equity are more likely to produce favourable institutional outcomes.

3. Demographic Factors and Leadership Preparedness: Mohnot (2017) examines demographic elements influencing leadership readiness, pinpointing age, leadership experience, and academic discipline as key determinants. This theme underscores the necessity for leadership development programs tailored to the specific characteristics of educational leaders.

4. Educational Governance and Managerialism: Middlehurst & Elton (1992) discuss the cybernetic governance model and the rising trend of managerialism in educational environments. This theme investigates the tension between collegiality and management,

alongside the long-term consequences of governance models prioritizing short-term managerial achievements over enduring collegial leadership.

5. Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership: Hartley (2004) highlights emotional intelligence as a pivotal aspect of transformational leadership. This theme emphasizes leaders' ability to effectively manage emotions, thereby enhancing their leadership impact. Emotional intelligence is vital for navigating complex institutional relationships and aligning leadership practices with centralized educational policy objectives.

6. Leadership and School Culture: Niemann & Kotze (2006) explore how leadership practices influence school culture, discovering a positive correlation between leadership methods and either sociability or solidarity. Their findings suggest that distinct leadership styles can nurture various organizational cultures.

7. Differentiating Educational Management and Leadership: Connolly, James, & Fertig (2017) provide a detailed evaluation of the distinctions between educational management and leadership, asserting that management is primarily task-oriented while leadership emphasizes influence. This distinction is crucial for understanding how leaders can handle administrative responsibilities alongside inspirational duties.

8. Trends in Educational Leadership Research: Heck & Hallinger (2005) identify emerging trends in educational leadership research, particularly the shift towards more humanistic and moral approaches. They advocate for increased empirical rigor in leadership studies to ensure future research addresses relevant and widely recognized challenges in the discipline.

Table: Summary of Studies Reviewed

Study	Leadership Model	Key Findings
Yelder & Codling (2004)	Academic-Managerial Blend	Dual-sector leadership; significance of shared leadership
Khan et al. (2021)	Transformational/Transactional	Organizational justice mediates leadership and performance
Hundessa (2019)	Democratic/Transformational	Leadership leans more towards managerial than visionary
Mohnot (2017)	Academic Leadership	Demographics significantly influence leadership preparedness
Middlehurst & Elton (1992)	Collegiality vs. Managerialism	Managerialism undermines traditional collegial governance
Connolly, James, & Fertig (2017)	Educational Leadership	Leadership necessitates balancing responsibility and influence

Findings:

Integration of Academic and Managerial Leadership: Research indicates that the combination of academic skills and managerial abilities results in more effective leadership. Yelder and Codling (2004) highlight the benefits of shared leadership within departments, enabling institutions to harness both research and operational strengths.

Impact of Organizational Justice: Khan et al. (2021) reveal that organizational justice is essential for enhancing institutional effectiveness. The principles of

fairness and transparency act as mediators between leadership styles and employee performance.

Demographic Influences: Studies suggest that a leader's age, experience, and academic discipline significantly affect their preparedness for leadership roles. Mohnot (2017) points out that leaders from humanities disciplines tend to be better prepared than those from natural sciences, indicating a need for tailored leadership training.

Challenges in Leadership Preparedness: Hundessa (2019) indicates a shortfall in leadership training

among departmental heads, who often perceive their roles as more managerial than visionary. This highlights the crucial need for structured leadership development programs.

Discussion:

Integrating Leadership Models: The review advocates for institutions to adopt a balanced strategy that melds academic and managerial leadership, addressing operational hurdles while preserving academic integrity.

The Role of Fairness in Leadership: The findings assert that organizational justice, as emphasized by Khan et al., should form a core aspect of leadership practices to enhance employee motivation and performance. Leaders must focus on transparency and equitable decision-making.

Preparing Future Leaders: It is essential for leadership training programs to consider demographic variables, as suggested by Mohnot (2017). Specifically tailored leadership initiatives can help close the preparedness gap, especially for individuals from underrepresented disciplines.

Challenges of Managerialism: The increase in managerialism, as discussed by Middlehurst and Elton (1992), risks degrading the collegial atmosphere of academia. Leaders must seek to maintain a balance between managerial tasks and fostering a collaborative academic culture.

Conclusion:

This review has investigated a variety of leadership models that merge academic and managerial expertise within educational institutions. The integration of these two fields is emphasized to enhance institutional effectiveness and strengthen leadership capacity. The function of organizational justice is crucial for mediating leadership effects on employee performance, reinforcing fairness and transparency as central leadership responsibilities. The study also highlights the necessity for customized leadership training programs that reflect demographic distinctions such as age, experience, and academic background. Future research should further explore the balance between academic and managerial leadership, particularly in light of the rising trend of managerialism in educational environments. By embracing a comprehensive approach to leadership, educational institutions can better traverse the complexities of modern governance and bolster their long-term success.

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